

Predicting Private Equity Fund Performance using Machine Learning: A Dual Approach to Classification and Return Forecasting

Undergraduate Dissertation

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Abstract

Private equity (PE) plays an increasingly central role in institutional portfolios yet forecasting fund performance remains challenging due to limited data, reporting opacity, and long investment horizons. This study applies machine learning (ML) to predict PE performance, defined by Net Internal Rate of Return (NIRR), using a dual modelling framework: a classification approach to identify top-quartile funds (NIRR>24%), and a quantitative (regression) approach to forecast NIRR as a continuous outcome. Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, and Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are implemented in both frameworks. In classification, ML models are benchmarked against logistic regression (Logit); in regression, against a naïve benchmark and linear models including Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Ridge, and Elastic Net. SVM achieved the highest classification performance (accuracy = 0.764, precision = 0.562, recall = 0.720, F1 score = 0.632, ROC AUC = 0.738), while XGBoost was most effective for NIRR forecasting (test MSE = 1.763, RMSE = 13.280, MAE = 7.961). SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) highlight fund-level features and macroeconomic indicators as key predictive drivers. These findings offer a scalable, interpretable framework to support data-driven fund selection for Limited Partners (LPs).

Keywords: Machine Learning, Private Equity, Forecasting, NIRR, Fund-level Features, Macroeconomic Variables, SHAP, Limited Partner (LP)

1. Introduction

Private Equity (PE) has become a core component of institutional portfolios over the past two decades, increasingly valued for its potential to generate alpha¹, provide diversification, and support long-term value creation. Since the early 2000s, global PE assets under management (AUM) have grown from under \$1 trillion to over \$13.1 trillion by 2023 (McKinsey & Company, 2024), driven by rising allocations from pension funds and sovereign wealth funds. These institutional investors, known as Limited Partners (LPs), commit capital to funds managed by General Partners (GPs), who oversee sourcing, executing, and divesting investments over a typical ten-year fund lifecycle. PE's appeal lies in its ability to deliver superior returns through operational improvements, strategic oversight, and active governance of portfolio companies (Kaplan & Strömberg, 2009). Performance is typically measured by the Net Internal Rate of Return (NIRR), defined as the annualised discount rate that equates the present value of all cash outflows with the present value of all cash inflows received by Limited Partners (LPs), net of fees and carried interest. This captures the net annualised return based on the timing and scale of cash flows. Despite critiques regarding its reinvestment assumptions, it remains the industry standard (Kaplan & Sensoy, 2015).

Concurrently, policymakers in developed economies have increasingly viewed PE as a vehicle for fostering innovation and long-term productivity. In the UK, regulatory and fiscal reforms aim to reduce barriers for asset managers and channel pension fund capital into private markets via vehicles such as Funds of Funds² (HM Treasury, 2024a; 2024b; 2025a). These reforms are underpinned by growing evidence that PE-backed firms outperform their peers on innovation, export activity, and productivity (Wilson et al., 2024). Similar momentum is visible in the EU's Capital Markets Union (CMU), which seeks to expand institutional investment into scale-ups and small-medium enterprises (Arampatzi et al., 2025), and in the US, revised ERISA guidance has broadened pension access to private markets (US Department of Labor, 2021). These developments reflect a broader policy shift positioning PE as central to economic growth and capital mobilisation strategies.

¹ Alpha refers to the excess return of an investment relative to a benchmark index, often interpreted as a measure of value added by the fund manager (Kaplan and Schoar, 2005).

² Fund of Funds is an investment vehicle that allocates capital across a diversified portfolio of PE funds, rather than investing directly in underlying companies (HM Treasury, 2025b).

Despite its increasing prominence, forecasting PE fund performance remains complex. Compared to public markets, PE is hindered by structural opacity, where valuation data is sparse and lagged, reporting is non-standardised, and performance becomes observable only years after capital commitment (Harris et al., 2014). This creates informational asymmetries between GPs and LPs, making it difficult to evaluate fund quality at the time of investment. Moreover, macroeconomic volatility, including COVID-19 disruptions, inflation shocks, and interest rate instability, has further increased the uncertainty surrounding fund outcomes (McKinsey and Company, 2024). These dynamics have amplified the need for data-driven tools that can support ex-ante, evidence-based capital allocation, particularly as policymakers push for more institutional exposure in private markets.

Against this backdrop, ML has emerged as a capable tool for forecasting complex, non-linear relationships, typical of PE datasets (Dudda and Hornuf, 2024; Xu et al., 2024). Applications of ML in finance, particularly in credit scoring (Bussmann et al., 2020) and equity forecasting (Wolf and Neugebauer, 2019), have grown substantially. Yet, within the PE domain, adoption remains limited. Most existing studies focus on binary classification, and few offer interpretable outputs (Sigrist and Perfetto, 2019; Lamothe-Fernández et al., 2024).

This study contributes and extends the existing literature in several ways. First, this study introduces a unified ML framework to evaluate both binary and continuous forecasting, reflecting the dual nature of real world fund-selection, where LPs may consider both categorical outcome (top-quartile of performing funds) and continuous return expectations (NIRR) (Phalippou, 2012). Second, the study benchmarks non-linear ML models (RF, XGBoost, SVM) against linear models (Logit, OLS, Ridge, Elastic Net) and a naïve benchmark, evaluating whether ML provides meaningful predictive improvements over conventional approaches. Third, this study moves beyond predictive accuracy by incorporating SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) to identify key drivers to address criticism of ML's 'black box' nature (Sigrist et al., 2023). This interpretability is essential for LPs, who face growing pressure to justify allocations in regulated environments.

Accordingly, this study has four primary research objectives: (a) develop a unified ML framework for forecasting PE fund performance, incorporating both classification and regression approaches (b) benchmark the predictive performance of non-linear ML models (RFs, XGBoost, and SVM) against traditional linear models (Logit, OLS, Ridge, Elastic Net)

and a naïve benchmark (c) employ SHAP to identify economically meaningful drivers of fund performance (d) provide actionable insights for LPs and policymakers seeking to optimise fund selection amid greater policy tailwinds.

These contributions advance the literature by being the first to adopt a unified modelling framework that simultaneously evaluates classification and regression approaches for PE forecasting, while incorporating economic context and ensuring model interpretability. By aligning model outputs with stakeholder decision-making needs, it enhances capital allocation in a financial landscape where PE is playing an increasingly strategic role.

The remainder of this study is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews relevant literature; Section 3 outlines the methodology; Section 4 details the dataset and feature engineering; Section 5 presents empirical findings and discussion; and Section 6 concludes with limitations and directions for future research.

2. Literature review

This section critically reviews the literature on predicting PE fund performance, with an emphasis on ML. As access to fund-level and macroeconomic data has improved, ML has emerged as a promising yet evolving tool in the PE domain. Two main modelling strands dominate: classification, which predicts whether a fund exceeds a performance threshold (IRR), and quantitative forecasting, which models continuous outcomes (IRR or cash flows). While most studies favour classification, often using ensemble methods such as RF and XGBoost, few address continuous prediction. This review traces the evolution from traditional econometric models to ML, highlighting methodological gaps and motivating the dual approach adopted in this study.

2.1 Traditional Econometric Approaches

Before the integration of ML, PE fund performance was typically modelled using linear techniques such as OLS. Kaplan and Schoar (2005) demonstrated strong performance persistence; GPs with historically high-performing funds were more likely to outperform in future vintages. Controlling for fund size, market timing, and firm characteristics, they observed procyclical fundraising, where increased capital inflows were negatively associated with future returns, suggesting diminishing returns to scale and heightened competition. These findings challenge the Efficient Market Hypothesis (Fama, 1970), where persistent outperformance and procyclical flows suggest that prices may not fully reflect all available information.

Harris et al. (2014) extended this, showing that traditional performance metrics, such as IRR and multiples, explained over 93% of the variation in Public Market Equivalent³, validating IRRs use as a reliable outcome measure.

While these studies established a foundational understanding of PE performance, their predictive scope is constrained by models assuming linearity. ML approaches address these limitations by capturing non-linear relationships and handling high dimensional structured data.

³ Public Market Equivalent compares the performance of a PE fund to a public market index by simulating how the fund's cash flows would have performed if invested in the public market over the same period (Harris et al., 2014).

2.2 Classification approach

Binary classification is widely used to predict PE fund performance, typically identifying whether a fund exceeds a set threshold. This mirrors investor decision-making focused on outperformance.

Sigrist and Perfetto (2019) applied RF using fund-level attributes, macroeconomic indicators, and track record variables to predict IRR thresholds. RF outperformed XGBoost and linear models, achieving an AUC of 0.674, though gains over OLS were marginal, suggesting limited capture of non-linear effects. Sigrist et al. (2023) extended this by incorporating SHAP for interpretability. Ross et al. (2021) evaluated VC exits (IPO or acquisition), finding XGBoost delivered the highest accuracy (89%) and AUC (0.959), confirming its potential in early-stage investing. Lamothe-Fernández et al. (2024) compared RF, SVM, Multilayer Perceptrons, and C4.5⁴ on PE fund classification. C4.5 achieved the highest accuracy (86.13%), followed by RF (81.81%) and SVM (81.57%), all outperforming the logit benchmark.

Beyond binary classification, Jones and Wang (2019) used TreeNet® gradient boosting to predict five distinct exit outcomes. AUC values reached 0.962 in binary settings and 0.751 for multi-class tasks, highlighting the value of gradient boosting for granular prediction.

2.3 Quantitative Approach

ML applications for predicting PE performance as a continuous outcome remain limited. Only three studies adopt this approach (Karatas et al., 2021; Tausch & Pietz, 2024; Kruglikov and Forthun, 2022⁵).

Karatas et al. (2021) used neural networks (NNs) to forecast quarterly cash flows, capturing the J-curve, where early capital calls generate negative flows followed by later distributions

⁴ C4.5 is a decision tree classification algorithm that is an extension of the earlier ID3 algorithm, developed by Ross Quinlan (1986) (Lamothe-Fernández et al., 2024).

⁵ Kruglikov and Forthun (2022) provides preliminary support for non-linear regression but their study lacks benchmarking and peer review, as it is a Master's thesis. Despite these limitations, it remains the only paper comparable to this study, making it relevant for contextualizing the current literature

(Meyer & Pierre-Yves, 2005). Their direct model outperformed their benchmark⁶ in MAE and RMSE, with further gains from incorporating macroeconomic indicators, such as GDP growth and equity indices. Tausch and Pietz (2024) proposed a hybrid method combining ML with asset pricing theory. Using a Stochastic Discount Factor (SDF) framework, they decomposed returns into market exposure and an idiosyncratic residual, which was modelled using L2 boosting. This approach shares core intuition with XGBoost's iterative improvement structure (section 3.2.1), capturing fund-specific non-linear effects. Kruglikov and Forthun (2022) applied SVM and NN to predict raw NIRR. SVM showed the lowest training MSE (0.0072) but performed poorly out-of-sample (MSE = 0.0577), likely due to overfitting. NN had a more balanced result (training MSE = 0.0423, test MSE = 0.0377), suggesting stronger generalisation. These findings underscore the importance of controlling model complexity in small datasets and suggest NNs may offer better reliability.

Whilst these studies offer important contributions, they remain relatively isolated within the broader literature. As such, the quantitative ML literature in PE remains nascent, with significant scope for methodological development.

2.4 Identifying the Gap in the Literature

This review highlights a shift from linear models toward ML, which better captures PE's complexity. Classification models, especially ensemble methods, show moderate improvements over logit, while multi-class models provide greater granularity. However, continuous prediction remains underdeveloped. Only Karatas et al. (2021) and Tausch and Pietz (2024) model returns directly, and neither benchmark ML against linear models.

To date, no study has jointly evaluated classification and regression models within a unified ML framework using cross-sectional data, nor combined fund-level and macroeconomic variables with interpretability tools. This study addresses these gaps by applying both classification and regression models, comparing non-linear and linear methods, and using SHAP to explain model predictions.

⁶ Karatas et al. (2021) benchmark constituted an 'indirect method', that predicted inputs to a traditional cash flow formula, known as the Yale model (Takahashi and Alexander, 2002).

Accordingly, the following hypotheses are proposed:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Non-linear ML models (RF, XGBoost, SVC) will outperform a logit benchmark in classifying top-performing funds, based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1, and ROC AUC

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Non-linear models (SVR, RF, XGBoost) will outperform a naïve benchmark and linear models (OLS, Ridge, Elastic Net) in predicting NIRR, evaluated by train/test MSE, RMSE, and MAE.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Key fund attributes, such as fund size, fund number, will emerge as the most influential predictors of NIRR, with macroeconomic indicators also contributing.

3. Methodology

This section outlines the dual methodological framework for evaluating ML models in predicting PE fund performance: a classification approach to identify top-quartile outperformers and a quantitative approach to forecast continuous fund-level returns via NIRR. This constitutes a cross-sectional, ex-ante prediction in which NIRR is forecast using only information available at fundraising, reflecting the LPs' decision-making context.

Both approaches incorporate the same ML models (RF, XGBoost, SVM), but differ in benchmarks. The classification models are compared to a logit benchmark; the regression models to a naïve benchmark and regularised linear models (OLS, Ridge, Elastic Net) (Figure 1). Ridge and Elastic Net offer L2 and combined L1–L2 regularisation, bridging traditional linear models and penalisation techniques common in ML.

Given the focus on ML, the linear models' underlying structures are assumed known. The remainder of the section introduces each ML model in both classification and quantitative settings, with emphasis on how their theoretical foundations address challenges in PE data, such as multicollinearity, class imbalance, and non-linearity. It concludes with an overview of model evaluation metrics and interpretability, ensuring modelling decisions are both methodologically grounded in the context of ML.

Figure 1: Methodology Outline

3.1 ML models

3.1.1 Random Forest (RF)

3.1.1.1 Classification

RF is a supervised ensemble learning method that improves predictive accuracy and reduces overfitting by aggregating the outputs of multiple decision trees through ‘bagging’. Each tree is trained on a bootstrapped⁷ data subset, with random feature selection at each split. This double randomness reduces tree correlation and improves model robustness (Breiman, 2001) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: RF Bagging

Once all trees are trained, predictions are made by majority vote across the total number of trees (K). The ensemble prediction, $H(x)$, represents the class that receives the most votes:

$$H(x) = \arg \max_y \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{I}(h_k(x) = y) \quad (1)$$

⁷A bootstrapped sample is a random sample drawn with replacement from the training set (Breiman, 2001).

where $h_k(x)$ is the prediction from the k -th tree, $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function, and $y \in Y$ represents the set of class labels⁸. Majority voting mitigates the high variance of individual trees, especially under noise or class imbalance (Liu et al., 2012).

Model confidence can be assessed via the margin function, which measures the difference between the average vote for the correct class and that for the most probable incorrect class. For an input X with true label Y , the margin is defined as:

$$mg(X, Y) = \mathbb{E}_{\Xi} \mathbb{I}(h(X, \Xi) = Y) - \max_{j \neq Y} \mathbb{E}_{\Xi} \mathbb{I}(h(X, \Xi) = j) \quad (2)$$

where Ξ denotes the random elements in tree construction (the bootstrap sample and random feature set). A positive margin implies correct classification, while a negative margin indicates a likely misclassification, demonstrating how the model distinguishes borderline cases (Liu et al., 2012). This is significant as PE fund performance often lies near IRR thresholds where small deviations alter investment decisions (Sigrist and Perfetto, 2019).

As the number of trees increases, the probability that the margin is negative (generalisation error) converges to a limit bounded by:

$$Prediction\ Error\ (PE^*) \leq \frac{1 - s^2}{s^2} \rho \quad (3)$$

where s denotes the strength⁹ of a tree and ρ is the correlation between trees. This highlights the ensemble trade-off; accurate and diverse trees yield lower error (Breiman, 2001). Where predictors may be multicollinear and noisy, RF's decorrelation mechanism enables RF to maintain predictive power under such conditions.

3.1.1.2 Quantitative

RF is also extended in the quantitative approach. In this context, each decision tree in the forest produces a numerical estimate, and the final RF prediction is obtained by averaging the

⁸ Y refers to the true class label of a specific observation, while y denotes a generic candidate label over which the model aggregates votes (Liu et al., 2012).

⁹ Strength is defined as the trees' accuracy relative to a random guess (Breiman, 2001).

outputs of all K trees in the ensemble (Breiman, 2001; Liu et al., 2012). Each tree is constructed from a bootstrapped sample of the data, and at each node, a random subset of predictors is selected. The prediction function is:

$$\hat{Y}(x) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K h_k(x) \quad (4)$$

where $h_k(x)$ is the output of the k -th tree for input x . This averaging reduces variance and stabilises predictions, yielding a robust approximation of the underlying regression function (Breiman, 2001).

As tree count increases, the RF estimator converges ‘almost surely’¹⁰ to the conditional mean (Liu et al., 2012):

$$\hat{Y}(x) \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[Y|X = x] \text{ almost surely as } K \rightarrow \infty \quad (5)$$

This implies that RF regression is a statistically consistent estimator of the true function given sufficient depth and data coverage. As a result, the model can capture complex, non-linear relationships between predictors and outcomes without assuming a specific functional form (Biau, 2012).

Moreover, the generalisation error of the forest is bounded by the average correlation among trees and their individual prediction errors:

$$PE_{forest}^* \leq \rho \cdot PE_{tree}^* \quad (6)$$

where ρ denotes the average correlation between tree predictions; ensemble performance improves with both accuracy (low PE_{tree}^*) and diversity across trees (low ρ).

¹⁰ ‘Almost surely’ refers to an event happens with probability 1, but not necessarily with absolute certainty. For example, there may be pathological case (e.g., due to randomness in bootstrap sampling or extreme data configurations) where convergence fails, however these cases are so rare that their probability is effectively zero (Liu et al., 2012).

Combined, these properties make RF a flexible and robust model for predicting PE fund performance, offering stability and generalisation in high-dimensional, noisy, and multicollinear settings, justifying its inclusion in both the classification and regression frameworks.

3.1.2 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

XGBoost, a supervised ensemble method, provides a unified boosting framework that is applied consistently across both the classification and quantitative approaches.

XGBoost constructs decision trees sequentially through a process known as ‘boosting’. In contrast to RF, which builds trees independently and aggregates predictions via majority vote, XGBoost trains each new tree to correct the residual errors of the current ensemble. Each iteration emphasises poorly predicted observations, reducing bias over time and improving accuracy (Chen & Guestrin, 2016) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: XGBoost ‘Boosting’

Formally, as shown by Chen & Guestrin (2016), XGBoost models the predicted outcome, \hat{y}_i for observation i as an additive ensemble of T trees:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(x_i), \text{ where } f_t \in \mathcal{F} \quad (7)$$

where each f_t is a decision tree mapping inputs x_i to a predicted score, and \mathcal{F} denotes the space of all possible trees. The model is trained by sequentially minimising an objective function combining prediction loss and model complexity:

$$\mathcal{L}^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(t)}) + \sum_{t=1}^T \Omega(f_t) \quad (8)$$

The first term $\ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i^{(t)})$ is a loss function that measures how closely the predicted value $\hat{y}_i^{(t)}$ matches the true outcome y_i . The loss function tends to be a logistic loss in classification approaches, and squared error loss in regression (Ciampiconi, 2024), thus the loss function is task dependent. The second term $\Omega(f_t)$ is a regularisation penalty designed to control the complexity of each tree, defined as:

$$\Omega(f_t) = \Gamma T + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{j=1}^T w_j^2 \quad (9)$$

where T is the number of leaves in tree f_t , w_j are leaf weights, and Γ, λ are penalties on depth and leaf magnitudes, respectively. This regularisation addresses the bias-variance trade-off, promoting generalisation by discouraging overly complex trees¹¹.

To optimise this objective efficiently, XGBoost employs a second-order Taylor expansion of the loss:

$$\tilde{\mathcal{L}}^{(t)} \approx \sum_{i=1}^n \left[g_i f_t(x_i) + \frac{1}{2} h_i f_t^2(x_i) \right] + \Omega(f_t) \quad (10)$$

where,

$$g_i = \left. \frac{\partial \ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i)}{\partial \hat{y}_i} \right|_{\hat{y}_i = \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)}} \quad (11)$$

¹¹ ΓT penalises trees with a large number of leaves, discouraging overly deep or complex models. $\frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{j=1}^T w_j^2$, applies L2 regularisation to the leaf weights, shrinking large predictions and smoothing the function surface Chen & Guestrin (2016).

$$h_i = \frac{\partial^2 \ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i)}{\partial \hat{y}_i^2} \Big|_{\hat{y}_i = \hat{y}_i^{(t-1)}} \quad (12)$$

g_i represents the gradient of loss with respect to the prediction, h_i represents the second derivative of loss, and $f_t(x_i)$ is the new score predicted by the new tree for observation i .

These derivatives guide tree construction by selecting optimal split points and assigning leaf weights that minimise the expanded loss¹². Incorporating curvature information allows faster and more stable convergence than gradient-only methods (Pachebat & Ivanov, 2022).

Therefore, the additive structure enables iterative refinement, particularly useful for borderline outperformers. Regularisation embedded in the objective controls overfitting in high-dimensional, collinear, and noisy data environments. These properties make XGBoost well-suited for both classification and quantitative prediction in PE.

3.1.3 Support Vector Machines (SVMs)

SVMs are supervised learning algorithms that improve predictive performance and robustness by focusing only on the most informative observations. Rather than fitting all data points equally, SVMs construct decision functions that maximise the margin (the distance between the decision boundary (hyperplane) and the closest training points). In classification, this margin is maximised (Section 3.2.3.1), while in regression, deviations within an ε -insensitive zone are ignored (Section 3.2.3.2). In both settings, the model relies on a sparse subset of training points (support vectors) which define the decision function (Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor, 2004) (Figure 4).

¹² It is important to note that the derivatives may vary depending on the choice of loss function, however the structure for the approximation remains the same across both structures (Ciampiconi, 2024).

Figure 4: SVM – Support Vector Classification (SVC) specific

Formally, in both classification and quantitative approaches, SVMs construct a prediction function of the form:

$$f(x) = w^T \phi(x) + b \quad (13)$$

where $\phi(x)$ is a transformation of the original input into a higher-dimensional feature space. This transformation is handled implicitly through a kernel function:

$$K(x_i, x_j) = \phi(x_i)^T \phi(x_j) \quad (14)$$

allowing SVMs to capture non-linearities without explicitly specifying interaction or polynomial terms (Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor, 2004).

In practice, different variants of the SVM framework are used depending on the prediction task: Support Vector Classification (SVC) is applied for binary classification problems, whereas Support Vector Regression (SVR) is used for continuous outcome prediction.

3.1.3.1 Classification and Support Vector Classification

In classification, SVCs seek the hyperplane that separates classes with the largest margin. Given labels¹³, $y_i \in \{-1,1\}$, the optimisation problem is:

$$\min_{w, b, \xi} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i \quad \text{s.t.} \quad y_i(w^\top \phi(x_i) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i \quad \text{for } \xi_i \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

$\|w\|^2$ penalises complexity, analogous to ridge regression, while slack variables ξ_i allow for soft-margin violations, which are particularly important when classes are not linearly separable. The regularisation parameter, C , balances classification accuracy against margin width; larger values prioritise data fit, whereas smaller values prioritise generalisation.

The dual form of a decision function is:

$$\hat{y}(x) = \text{sign} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x) + b \right) \quad (16)$$

where α_i are dual coefficients determined during optimisation. Only support vectors (points with $\alpha_i > 0$) contribute to this expression (final decision). This makes the model sparse, interpretable, and robust to outliers or noise in the training data (Smola and Schölkopf, 2004).

3.1.3.2 Quantitative and Support Vector Regression

In regression, SVRs aim to approximate y_i , while allowing deviations up to ε . Observations within this epsilon-insensitive zone incur no penalty, whereas those outside are penalised linearly (Smola and Schölkopf, 2004). The optimisation problem is:

$$\min_{w, b, \xi, \xi^*} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n (\xi_i + \xi_i^*) \quad (17)$$

The objective function introduces two slack variables for each observation ($\xi_i + \xi_i^*$), representing overshooting and undershooting beyond the ε -tube (Figure 5). The prediction function is:

¹³ $y_i \in \{-1,1\}$ refers to the binary class label (e.g., top-quartile fund vs. non-top-quartile).

$$\hat{y}(x) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) K(x_i, x) + b \right) \quad (18)$$

Only points outside the ε -tube (those with $|\hat{y}_i - y_i| > \varepsilon$) contribute to the model, yielding a sparse and interpretable solution. This makes SVR particularly well-suited to financial return modelling, where minor deviations may be treated as noise and only larger errors should influence learning and fitting.

Figure 5: SVR and Epsilon Tube

The mathematical structure of SVMs, including the regularisation through $\|w\|^2$, kernel-based non-linearity, and sparsity through support vectors, makes them well-suited to the challenges of PE data, justifying their inclusion in both the classification and quantitative approaches (Smola and Schölkopf, 2004; Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor, 2004).

3.2 Model Implementation and Hyperparameter Tuning

All models were implemented in Python using JupyterLab. The ‘scikit-learn’ package was used for linear models, RFs, and SVMs; ‘xgboost’ for gradient boosting; and ‘shap’ for interpretability. Hyperparameters were selected via grid or randomised search with three-fold cross-validation (GridSearchCV, RandomizedSearchCV).

3.3 Model Evaluation Metrics

3.3.1 Classification Approach

Classification performance is evaluated using several metrics derived from the confusion matrix (Figure 6), which compares predicted and actual class labels across four outcomes: true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN).

In this study, a TP occurs when a top-quartile fund is correctly classified as an outperformer, while a FN reflects a missed opportunity to identify such a fund. Conversely, a FP arises when an underperformer is incorrectly predicted to outperform, and a TN is a correct rejection of an underperformer. These misclassifications carry practical consequences, where FP may lead to overcommitting capital to weak funds, while FN risks overlooking high-return opportunities (Sigrist and Perfetto, 2019).

Figure 6: Confusion Matrix

		Actual (Model)	
		Positive	Negative
Predicted (Target)	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)
	Negative	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)

Accuracy measures the overall proportion of correctly classified funds:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN} \quad (19)$$

While informative, accuracy can be misleading in imbalanced datasets (Naidu et al., 2023; Obi, 2023), as is the PE dataset used in this study (Section 4), and must be interpreted alongside class-sensitive metrics.

Precision evaluates how many predicted top-quartile funds are truly outperformers:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (20)$$

This reflects the model's ability to avoid misclassifying underperformers as outperformers, which is critical when poor fund selection leads to misallocated capital (Fuchs et al., 2016).

Recall measures how many actual top-quartile funds are correctly identified:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (21)$$

High recall reduces the risk of missing promising funds, an important consideration given the high opportunity cost of FN (Naidu et al., 2023).

F1-Score provides a harmonic mean of precision and recall:

$$F1 \text{ Score} = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{Precision} + \frac{1}{Recall}} = 2 \cdot \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R} \quad (22)$$

This is particularly valuable in imbalanced settings, where it captures the trade-off between identifying genuine outperformers and avoiding false signals.

Receiving Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve plots the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR) across classification thresholds.

$$True \text{ positive rate } (TPR) = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (23)$$

$$False \text{ positive rate } (FPR) = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (24)$$

Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) aggregates this trade-off into a single scalar between 0.5 (random guessing) and 1 (perfect classification) (Figure 7). AUC is widely used as a threshold-independent measure of model discrimination. Importantly, it remains robust in the presence of class imbalance (Luque et al., 2019; Thabtah et al., 2020).

Figure 7: Illustrative ROC Curve

3.3.2 Quantitative Approach

Regression performance is evaluated using three error-based metrics; Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). These assess the discrepancy between predicted and actual NIRR, providing insight on model accuracy and robustness (Tatachar, 2021; Plevris et al., 2022).

MSE measures the average of the squared differences between predicted and observed values:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (25)$$

where, n denotes number of predictions, y_i denotes observed values, \hat{y}_i denotes predicted values.

MSE penalises larger errors more heavily due to the squaring term, making it sensitive to extreme deviations. A high MSE may indicate the model's inability to accurately capture extreme performance outcomes, which is an important concern when misprediction of outlier fund performance can distort portfolio decisions (Plevris et al., 2022).

RMSE is the square root of MSE:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (26)$$

By expressing the error in the same units as NIRR, RMSE enhances interpretability and facilitates comparison across models.

MAE calculates the average of the absolute differences between predicted and actual values:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (27)$$

Contrastingly to MSE and RMSE, MAE treats all deviations equally and is less sensitive to outliers (Tatachar, 2021). This makes it well-suited to skewed or heavy-tailed return distributions, where robustness is key to assessing model consistency across the full range of outcomes. Combined, these metrics ensure a balanced evaluation of regression performance, where both precision and robustness are essential for reliable return prediction in PE performance.

3.3.3 SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations)

To complement statistical evaluation, SHAP is used to interpret individual feature contributions. Based on cooperative game theory, SHAP decomposes each prediction into additive feature attributions, capturing average marginal effects while accounting for interactions (Lundberg and Lee, 2017; Siemers and Bajorath, 2023). Unlike local surrogate methods such as LIME, SHAP provides consistent local and global explanations. This enables identification of the most influential predictors across the full outcome distribution (Man & Chan, 2020).

4. Data

This section outlines the construction, structure, and transformation of the dataset used in both the classification and quantitative modelling frameworks. It begins with an overview of the raw data sources and variables, followed by a description of the cleaning, encoding, and preprocessing steps required for ML. Each transformation is grounded in methodological best practice, ensuring analytical robustness and model compatibility. The full pipeline is summarised in Figure 8.

4.1 Dataset Overview

This study draws on a manually compiled dataset combining fund-level data from Preqin with macroeconomic variables from Bloomberg. The sample includes 441 PE funds with vintage years from 2000 to 2020¹⁴, comprising 283 buyout and 158 growth equity vehicles; 272 focus on North America and 169 on Europe. Macroeconomic and market variables were aligned to each fund by vintage year, ensuring temporal consistency with fund-level characteristics and broader economic conditions. The dataset includes both numerical and categorical variables, summarised in Tables 1a and 1b.

Table 1a presents descriptive statistics. The target variable, NIRR (%), has a mean of 17.89%, with moderate right skew (0.70) and light-tailed kurtosis (1.72), supporting subsequent winsorisation and standardisation. Among fund-level predictors, AUM exhibits high dispersion (SD = 30,422) and extreme right skew (4.57), reflecting capital concentration among large GPs (McKinsey & Company, 2023). Final Close Size exhibits comparable skew (3.68) and heavy-tailed kurtosis (15.89), motivating log transformation.

PE market variables, particularly Dry Powder and Number of Funds Raised, display wide annual variation and non-normality. Dry Powder is especially skewed (3.15) with high dispersion (SD = 573,779). Macroeconomic indicators are more symmetric but still fail normality tests. GDP Growth shows mild negative skew (-1.43) and moderate kurtosis (2.64), reinforcing the need for transformation.

¹⁴ Funds covered within vintages 2000 to 2020 only due to annual PE market data limitations.

Table 1a: Raw Dataset Overview (numerical)

Variables	Description	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Coef. Var	Skewness	Kurtosis	NormTest	p-value	Data Source
Output variable										
NIRR (%)	Net internal rate of return of the fund, net of fees	17.89	14.37	14.52	0.86	0.70	1.72	0.00	0.00	Preqin
Fund Management Experience										
Fund Number (Overall)	The total number of funds raised by the fund manager across all strategies	3.11	2.00	2.60	0.83	3.42	21.12	0.00	0.00	Preqin
Fund Number (Series)	The fund's sequence number within its specific strategy series (e.g., Fund 2).	2.80	2.00	1.87	0.67	1.28	1.29	0.00	0.00	Preqin
Fund Manager Total AUM (USD Mn)	Total assets under management by the fund's GP	14481	5000	30422	2.10	4.57	25.07	0.00	0.00	Preqin
Fund's Strategy										
Final Close Size (USD Mn)	Total capital committed to the fund at final close	631	323	987	1.56	3.68	15.89	0.00	0.00	Preqin
PE Market Variables (annual)										
Number of Funds Raised	Number of funds raised globally in the same vintage year.	1266	1211	567	0.45	2.33	12.31	0.00	0.00	Preqin
Dry Powder (USD Mn)	Aggregate unspent committed capital in the PE market in the vintage year.	1246453	1311800	573779	0.46	1.33	3.15	0.00	0.00	Preqin
Capital Raised (USD Mn)	Total capital raised by funds globally in the same vintage year	371679	350760	205933	0.55	0.70	0.29	0.00	0.00	Preqin

Macroeconomic Variables (annual)

Variable	89.23	88.74	19.61	0.22	0.81	0.74	0.00	Bloomberg
Stock Market (Base=100)	Indexed value of public equity market performance for the vintage year and primary investment region: Stoxx 600 for Europe and S&P 500 for North America							
Bond Yield (Base=100)	65.38	68.16	17.55	0.27	-0.97	0.64	0.00	Bloomberg
	Indexed yield on sovereign bonds for the vintage year and primary investment region: Euro 10-year gov bond yield for Europe and US 10-year treasury yield for North America							
GDP growth (%)	2.14	2.20	1.47	0.69	-1.43	2.64	0.00	Bloomberg
	Annual GDP growth of the fund's primary investment region							

Figure 8: Data Transformation Pipeline

Normality is rejected for all variables at the 1% level (Shapiro-Wilk $p < 0.01$), empirically justifying the transformation and standardisation procedures. Table 1b summarises the categorical predictors, which capture discrete fund characteristics widely used in PE (Kaplan and Schoar, 2005; Karatas et al., 2021).

Table 1b: Raw Dataset overview (categorical)

Variables	Categories	Description	Source
Fund's Strategy			
Fund Type	2	Includes fund type categories: Buyout and Growth Equity	Preqin
Geography	2	Includes geographical type categories: Europe or North America	Preqin
Fund size	3	Includes fund size categories: Small (<500Mn), Mid (500Mn-1.5Bn), Large (>1.5Bn)	Preqin
Industry	6	Includes industry categories: Technology and Media, Healthcare and Pharmaceutical, Financial and Business Services Consumer and Retail, Energy and Infrastructure, or Diversified	Preqin

4.2 Data Transformation

4.2.1 Train-Test Split

To ensure fair and unbiased model evaluation, the dataset was 80/20 split into training and test sets before any transformation. Stratified sampling was applied in classification to preserve the proportion of top-quartile funds. Thus, the dataset is imbalanced, with only 28% of observations falling into the top NIRR quartile. However, this reflects the real-world distribution of private equity outcomes, where top-performing funds are a minority.

All transformations were fit to the training set only. Parameters such as means and standard deviations (for standardisation), category mappings (for encoding), and winsorisation thresholds were then applied to the test set. This prevents data leakage and preserves the test set as an unbiased proxy for unseen data (Kuhn & Johnson, 2013).

4.2.2 Data Cleaning and Preprocessing

Observations without reported NIRR were excluded. Among the remaining variables, missing values were imputed using K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), which leverages multivariate similarity and avoids the bias of mean or median imputation. This is well-suited to datasets with nonlinear dependencies (Acuña & Rodríguez, 2004).

To address distributional asymmetries, log transformations were applied to reduce right skew and compress extreme values. Winsorisation at the 1st and 99th percentiles further limited outlier influence. A small number of remaining cases were trimmed where these steps failed to sufficiently stabilise the distribution (Werner, 2023).

These steps reduce noise, correct distortions, and improve comparability across variables, while preserving the data structure.

4.2.3 Feature Engineering and Multicollinearity

Polynomial and interaction terms were introduced to reflect theoretically grounded relationships in PE. These transformations allow linear models to approximate nonlinear behaviour and can improve structure recognition in non-linear models (Powers et al., 2018). Table 2 presents the engineered terms with brief justifications.

Multicollinearity was assessed using a correlation matrix and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). As shown in Figure 9, most predictors are weakly correlated with NIRR, however Number of Funds raised, Capital Raised and Dry Powder exhibit strong intercorrelations.

VIF analysis (Appendix A) identified predictors exceeding the conventional threshold of 10 (Gujarati, 1995). Number of Funds Raised was removed. Although Capital Raised was also near the cutoff, it was retained after confirming it did not inflate the VIFs of other predictors.

Table 2: Polynomial and Interaction Terms

Variables	Description	Empirical Justification
Interaction Terms		
FundNumber (Series) x GDP	Captures how fund sequencing experience interacts with macroeconomic growth conditions	In expansionary periods, repeated fundraising may underperform due to capital overhang and market crowding, constraining even skilled GPs (Kaplan & Schoar, 2005).
AUM x FundNumber (Series)	Tests the interaction between GP scale and fund-raising experience	Frequent capital raising by large GPs may lead to underperformance from deployment pressure and managerial overstretch (Lopez-de-Silanes et al., 2015).
GDP x StockMarket	Measures economic–market cycle alignment.	Alignment between GDP growth and public equity markets enhances exit timing and valuations; misalignment restricts exits and lowers returns (Phalippou, 2009).
Capital Raised x StockMarket	Joint indicator of investor sentiment and fund inflows.	PE fundraising is procyclical; bull markets increase inflows, which can inflate valuations and lower future returns (Lerner et al., 2007).
DryPowder x Capital Raised	Captures the saturation of investable capital in PE markets.	Excess capital intensifies deal competition, driving up entry valuations and reducing selectivity (Jenkinson et al., 2013).
Fund Type x StockMarket	Tests sensitivity of growth equity strategies to public market conditions.	Growth equity funds depend on high-valuation public exits, increasing exposure to market swings (Metrick & Yasuda, 2010).
BondYield x FinalCloseSize	Captures interest rate effects on larger, potentially more leveraged funds.	High interest rates raise debt costs, constraining leverage and fund scalability (Axelson et al., 2012).
Polynomials		
FundManagerAUM ²	Captures diminishing marginal returns to GP scale.	Scale can offer efficiency, but excessive AUM leads to coordination frictions and reduced deal agility (Lopez-de-Silanes, 2015).
StockMarket ²	Captures nonlinear exposure to public equity markets, such as asymmetric effects of market booms vs. downturns.	PE funds benefit from upswings but may mistime exits during sharp rallies or volatile periods, reducing performance (Minardi et al., 2019).

Figure 9: Correlation Heatmap

4.2.4 Encoding and Standardisation

Categorical variables were encoded to meet model requirements. For linear models, one-hot encoding (OHE) was applied with drop-first encoding to avoid multicollinearity and the dummy variable trap. Resulting binary indicators were excluded from standardisation. OHE preserves interpretability and supports the assumption of additive, independent effects (Alaya et al., 2019). For non-linear models, ordinal encoding was used to avoid sparse matrices and improve stability on smaller datasets (Kunanbayev et al., 2021).

Following encoding, continuous numerical variables were Z-score standardised to zero mean and unit variance. This is essential for regularised linear and kernel-based models, which are sensitive to feature scaling (Kuhn & Johnson, 2013) (Appendix B for Kernel Density Estimates of NIRR across the data transformations).

5. Empirical Results

This section presents the empirical findings of the ML models applied to predict PE fund performance. Building on the methodologies outlined in Section 3, the findings are structured in two parts. First, a classification-based approach, assessing the ability of RF, XGBoost, and SVC to distinguish top-quartile funds based on a binary outperformance threshold of 24% NIRR. Second, a quantitative forecasting approach that models NIRR as a continuous outcome, comparing predictive accuracy of linear (OLS, Ridge, Elastic Net) and non-linear (RF, XGBoost, SVR) models. To support interpretability, SHAP analysis is used to identify the most influential predictors in the best-performing model.

5.1 Classification Approach

5.1.1 Summary Metrics

Table 3 summarises the out-of-sample classification performance of the logit benchmark alongside the RF, XGBoost, and SVC models. The analysis is based on five metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and ROC AUC. These combined measurements provide a comprehensive assessment of model performance, discussed in Section 3 (Obi, 2023).

Table 3: Out-of-sample Performance Metrics for RF, XGBoost, SVC

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	ROC AUC
Logit	0.623	0.399	0.576	0.503	0.598
RF	0.685	0.455	0.600	0.517	0.639
XGBoost	0.708	0.485	0.640	0.552	0.683
SVC	0.764	0.562	0.720	0.632	0.738

The logit model serves as a benchmark for evaluating ML performance. It delivers the weakest results, with accuracy of 0.623 and ROC AUC of 0.598, only marginally above random chance. Its low precision (0.399) highlights a high incidence of FPs, while its F1 score (0.503) and recall (0.576) indicate that although it identifies some top-performing funds, it lacks the discriminative power and balance necessary for robust fund classification.

SVC achieves the best performance across all metrics, with an accuracy (0.764), meaning that more than 76% of classification predictions are correct. Furthermore, SVC exceeds the other models in both recall (0.720) and precision (0.562), resulting in the highest F1 score (0.632), indicating an optimal balance between properly identifying successful funds and minimising FPs. The model has the highest ROC AUC (0.738), indicating higher discriminatory power (Figure 10). A brief dip below the 45-degree line at high FP rates (FPR > 0.8) reflects over-lenient thresholds that inflate FPs, highlighting the importance of threshold calibration in illiquid PE settings (Jeni et al., 2013; Davis & Goadrich, 2006).

Figure 10: ROC AUC for SVC

XGBoost ranks second-best overall, with gains in recall (0.640) and F1 score (0.552) compared to RF. Although its precision (0.485) is slightly lower than SVC's, XGBoost remains an effective classifier for identifying outperforming funds, albeit with a slightly higher FP rate.

RF exhibits the weakest performance across all metrics. Whilst its recall (0.600) indicates some success in detecting outperformers, its low precision (0.455) leads to a greater proportion of FPs, culminating in the lowest F1 score (0.517) among the three ML models.

5.1.2 Confusion Matrix Analysis

To provide a more granular understanding on the performance differences, Figure 11 illustrates the confusion matrices for each model, detailing distribution of TPs, FPs, TNs, and FNs (Section 3.3.1). This shows how predictions are distributed across classes.

Figure 11: Normalised Confusion Matrices for (a) SVC (b) XGboost (c) RF

SVC delivers the most balanced classification, correctly identifying 20% of total observations as TP and 56% as TN. It also records the lowest FP (16%) and FN (8%) rates, indicating a strong ability to distinguish outperformers while minimising misclassification by limiting both FP and FN.

XGBoost yields a slightly lower TP rate (18%) and higher FN rate (10%), reflecting weaker recall relative to SVC. Its TN rate (53%) is comparable, but the elevated FN rate suggests a higher likelihood of missing high-performing funds.

RF achieves the lowest TP rate (17%) and the greatest FN rate (11%), representing the lowest sensitivity among the models. Although its TN rate (52%) is reasonable, high FP and FN rates reflect weak class discrimination.

5.1.3 Summary Evaluation of Classifier Performance

The classification results show that SVC consistently outperforms RF and XGBoost across all evaluation metrics, highlighting SVC’s superior ability to distinguish between top and bottom-quartile funds across varying thresholds. While all models demonstrate some degree

of discriminatory power, SVC achieves the most effective balance between identifying outperformers and limiting false classifications.

However, the classification approach is inherently constrained by its binary structure. By converting continuous fund outcomes into categorical labels, it masks variation in the degree of outperformance among top-quartile funds. To address this limitation, the next section turns to a quantitative forecasting framework, which models NIRR as a continuous variable. This enables models not only to identify outperformers, but also to estimate the magnitude of expected returns.

5.2 Quantitative Approach

5.2.1 Error Metrics

Table 4 displays the performance of all seven models, including both linear and non-linear, used to forecast standardised NIRR. Evaluation was conducted on both training and test sets using MSE, RMSE, and MAE. The combined use of these metrics enables a comprehensive assessment of forecasting performance (Tatachar, 2021; Plevris et al., 2022).

Table 4: Forecasting Performance Metrics for all Models Predicting Standardised NIRR¹⁵

	Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test
	MSE	MSE	RMSE	RMSE	MAE	MAE
Naïve	2.250	2.250	15.000	15.000	12.000	12.000
OLS	2.104	2.197	14.504	14.823	9.740	9.060
Ridge	2.186	2.072	14.786	14.391	9.635	8.624
Elastic Net	2.159	2.113	14.694	14.537	9.611	8.576
RF	1.673	1.927	12.936	13.883	8.232	8.372
XGBoost	1.539	1.763	12.407	13.280	7.722	7.961
SVR	1.769	2.028	13.301	14.243	9.359	8.513

¹⁵ NIRR variable was standardised (with an initial standard deviation of approximately 15%), therefore the test RMSE values can be read as approximate percentage point prediction errors by scaling appropriately (for example, a standardised RMSE of 1.0 translates to 15 percentage points of return error).

The naïve benchmark, which predicts the sample mean for all funds, yields a test RMSE of 15.000 and a test MAE of 12.000. This establishes a simple yet informative benchmark for evaluating model performance. All subsequent models outperform this benchmark across all error metrics, indicating that the selected features capture meaningful variation in fund-level outcomes and contribute valuable signal in forecasting NIRR.

5.2.2 Linear Model Performance

Comparing the linear models, Ridge regression demonstrates the strongest out-of-sample performance, achieving a lower test MSE (2.072), RMSE (14.391), and MAE (8.624) than OLS. Interpreting the RMSE in the context of standardised NIRR, Ridge's test RMSE indicates the model's predictions deviates from actual returns by approximately ± 14.4 percentage points on average. This reduction in forecast error, from the naïve benchmark, reflects the benefits of L2 regularisation for improving model robustness.

Elastic Net offers similar performance, with a test RMSE of 14.537 and MAE of 8.576. However, these marginal differences suggest that the added flexibility of combining L1 and L2 penalties does not yield meaningful gains in this setting. This implies that increased model complexity does not guarantee improved performance without sufficient structural justification in the data (Shawe-Taylor et al., 1998).

The Ridge test set plot (Figure 12d) illustrates these dynamics. While the model captures the general upward trend in NIRR, prediction errors increase at the extremes. This highlights the limitations of linear models in modelling non-linear relationships, even with the inclusion of polynomial and interaction terms.

5.2.3 Non-Linear Model Performance

Non-linear models yield notable improvements in forecasting standardised NIRR. XGBoost achieves the strongest out-of-sample results, delivering the lowest test MSE (1.763), RMSE (13.280), and MAE (7.961). Interpreting RMSE, this implies that test predictions deviate from actual fund returns by approximately ± 13.3 percentage points on average. The MAE

Figure 12: Actual vs Predicted Standardised NIRR for (a) Train Set XGBoost (b) Test Set XGBoost (c) Test Set SVR (d) Test Set Ridge

(7.961) further indicates that typical prediction errors fall within ± 8.0 percentage points. The lower MAE implies infrequent large errors, reinforcing XGBoost’s reliability. Moreover, the relatively narrow gap between train MSE (1.539) and test MSE (1.763) reflects limited overfitting, suggesting strong generalisation to unseen data. The model’s use of boosting and shrinkage likely contributes to its capacity to capture complex, high-dimensional interactions while maintaining out-of-sample robustness (Chen & Guestrin, 2016). This is supported by Figure 12a and 12b; the training plot shows predictions densely clustered along the 45-degree line, and the test plot retains a strong linear structure with modest dispersion, illustrating both model fit and generalisation strength.

RF demonstrates strong predictive performance, with a test RMSE of 13.883 and MAE of 8.372, suggesting that RF forecasts deviate from actual standardised fund returns by approximately ± 13.9 and ± 8.4 percentage points, respectively. Whilst these results are comparable to XGBoost, RF is marginally less accurate across all test metrics. The train-test MSE gap (1.673 vs. 1.927) is modest, indicating good generalisation and limited overfitting. SVR shows moderate out-of-sample performance, with a test RMSE of 14.243 and MAE of 8.513. SVR's predictions deviate by approximately ± 14.2 percentage points on average, with typical errors around ± 8.5 percentage points. Although the core structure of the NIRR distribution is captured, its predictive variance is higher than that of XGBoost and RF. SVR follows the perfect prediction line at mid-range but shows greater tail dispersion (Figure 12c). While SVR offers improvements over linear models, it lacks the ensemble depth compared to the ensemble methods (XGBoost and RF).

5.2.4 Model Selection

While regularised linear models (Ridge and Elastic Net) outperform OLS, the largest gains come from non-linear ensemble methods. XGBoost achieves the strongest forecasting performance across all evaluation metrics. Its ability to model complex, high-dimensional interactions while generalising effectively to unseen data makes it the most accurate and reliable model for predicting PE fund performance in a continuous framework.

5.2.5 SHAP-Based Importance Analysis

Building on the identification of XGBoost as the most effective forecasting model, this section applies SHAP to examine the predictors most influential to its NIRR estimates. Figure 13a ranks the top 15 features by their mean absolute SHAP values, providing a global view of variable importance. Figure 13b complements this with a beeswarm plot, showing how individual observations are affected by each feature. Each dot represents a single fund, where the horizontal position shows the feature's marginal impact on predicted NIRR, while colour reflects the standardised value (red = high, blue = low).

Figure 13: (a) Top 15 Features Importances with a 95% CI (b) Beeswarm SHAP Plot¹⁶

The most important variable is $\text{FundNumber}^{17} \times \text{GDP}$, contributing over 0.10 standard deviations to predicted NIRR on average (Figure 13a). Higher values of this interaction (red dots) are generally associated with negative SHAP values, suggesting that raising multiple funds during periods of strong GDP growth is linked to lower returns (Figure 13b). The next most important feature, $\text{AUM} \times \text{FundNumber}$, reinforces this conclusion, where high values of this interaction are similarly associated with negative SHAP values.

Final Close Size also ranks highly but exhibits a wide SHAP value range, with both positive and negative effects depending on context, indicating heterogeneous, non-linear influence (Lamothe-Fernández et al., 2024).

Macroeconomic variables are also among the top 15 contributors. Notably, Stock Market and Bond Yield both exhibit consistent negative directional effects, with higher values generally associated with lower predicted NIRR. Although their individual contributions are smaller relative to the leading interaction terms, their consistent effects indicate that the model systematically incorporates macroeconomic signals into its predictions.

Thus, SHAP highlights a mix of directional effects and interaction-driven non-linearities across fund-specific and macroeconomic variables. These findings illustrate the

¹⁶ Stockmarket.1 corresponds to Stockmarket²

¹⁷ FundNumber refers to Fund Number (Series)

interpretability benefits of SHAP in complex, high-dimensional settings. Further economic interpretation of these patterns is provided in the following discussion.

5.3 Discussion

This study offers several key findings across both classification and regression frameworks. Firstly, in the classification approach, SVC proved most effective in distinguishing between top and bottom-quartile funds, outperforming XGBoost and RF across all metrics: accuracy (0.764), precision (0.562), recall (0.720), F1 score (0.632), and ROC AUC (0.738). By contrast, the logit model benchmark achieved a ROC AUC of 0.598, indicating weaker discriminatory power. These results confirm H1, supporting the superior performance of non-linear models over traditional logit models in classifying outperformers. These findings align Sigrist et al. (2023), who also apply ML to PE performance. However, while Sigrist et al. (2023) identified XGBoost as the top model (AUC = 0.659), followed by RF (AUC = 0.632), this study finds stronger performance from SVC. This highlights the benefits of extending model selection beyond tree-based ensembles. Furthermore, this study expands on previous work by incorporating a broader suite of performance metrics, enabling greater sensitivity to class imbalance.

Secondly, the quantitative approach identifies XGBoost as the most effective model for forecasting standardised NIRR. Compared to the naïve benchmark and five alternative models, it achieved the lowest test MSE (1.763), RMSE (13.280), MAE (7.961), with minimal overfitting. These results confirm H2, demonstrating that non-linear models outperform linear approaches in predicting fund-level performance. This finding contributes empirical evidence to a relatively underexplored area of ML and PE research. Kruglikov and Forthun (2022), is the only notable comparison. After standardising their reported test MSEs using comparable methodology and variance assumptions¹⁸, their best-performing non-linear model (NN) implied a deviation of ± 20.8 percentage points from actual returns. In contrast, this study achieves a substantially tighter error range, with a 7.5 percentage point reduction in forecast deviation, underscoring the predictive value of the selected features and modelling approach.

Thirdly, the divergence in optimal models across classification and regression approaches reflects fundamental differences in algorithmic structure and objective function, as outlined in Section 3. While SVC performs best in classification, XGBoost leads in continuous

¹⁸ $\sigma^2 = 0.0225$, based on this dataset's standard deviation of 15%, which is applied to Kruglikov and Forthun (2022) reported Test MSE of 0.1923 to calculate RMSE.

prediction. SVC constructs a maximum-margin hyperplane, optimising classification boundaries based on a subset of support vectors (Section 3.1.3.1). This makes it particularly effective in high-dimensional, binary classification tasks with limited signal or noisy boundaries, conditions typical of imbalanced fund performance classification (Maldonado et al., 2014). XGBoost is optimised for continuous outcomes through gradient boosting, where trees are sequentially constructed to minimise residual errors (Section 3.1.2). Its ability to model complex, non-linear interactions and non-monotonic effects across the feature space is well-suited to forecasting standardised NIRR, a task characterised by heterogeneity and high variance. Unlike linear models, which impose additive effects, or kernel-based regressors, which may overfit in noisy settings, XGBoost flexibly captures intricate return dynamics, consistent with results seen in other continuous prediction domains such as house price modelling (Sharma et al., 2024).

Fourth, this study finds that interaction effects between fund characteristics and macroeconomic indicators significantly influence predicted NIRR, confirming H3. The SHAP analysis identifies $\text{FundNumber} \times \text{GDP}$ as the most influential variable, exhibiting a negative contribution at higher values. This suggests that GPs raising multiple funds during periods of strong economic growth tend to underperform, consistent with the view that procyclical fundraising leads to capital overhang, valuation pressure, and reduced selectivity (Kaplan & Schoar, 2005). Similarly, the negative contribution of $\text{AUM} \times \text{FundNumber}$ reflects diminished returns among larger GPs who raise capital frequently. This may be due to deployment pressure and organisational overstretch (Lopez-de-Silanes et al., 2015). Together, these findings underscore how the scale and timing of fundraising can compound performance risks during market expansions, further challenging the EMH (Fama, 1970).

Fifth, while capital oversupply typically suppresses returns through inflated valuations, the SHAP analysis also reveals context-dependent positive effects, particularly for Final Close Size. This feature ranks among the top contributors, with SHAP values spread across both positive and negative ranges. Such symmetry suggests that fund size enhances performance under certain conditions, specifically, when managerial capacity is high and agency frictions are limited (Bernile, Cumming & Lyandres, 2007). These findings correspond to the non-linear patterns identified in Table 2 and reflect the capacity of XGBoost to capture marginal effects that vary across the feature space. This contrasts with linear models, which impose fixed functional relationships and may obscure such heterogeneity.

Sixth, macroeconomic indicators also rank among the top predictors, reinforcing the need to include them in ML-based PE forecasting. SHAP values for Stock Market and Bond Yield are consistently negative at higher values, indicating that elevated public equity valuations and rising interest rates are associated with lower expected NIRR. This is consistent with opportunity cost and valuation compression effects; Steger (2017) and Metrick & Yasuda (2010) show that high bond yields raise financing costs, while market peaks increase the risk of mistimed exits, validating these directional effects.

Following the analysis presented, it is confirmed that Hypotheses 1,2, and 3 are empirically supported.

6. Conclusions and Outlook

6.1 Summary of Findings

This study provides empirical support for all three hypotheses. First, H1 is confirmed, as non-linear models outperform the logit benchmark in the classification framework. SVC achieved the highest accuracy (0.764) and ROC AUC (0.738), outperforming both RF and XGBoost. Second, H2 is supported by the regression results, where XGBoost delivered the lowest test RMSE (13.280) and MAE (7.961), outperforming naïve and linear models in predicting standardised NIRR. These findings reinforce the superior forecasting performance of non-linear ML models and align with existing literature (Sigrist and Perfetto, 2019). Third, SHAP analysis supports H3, showing that fund-level characteristics and macroeconomic context significantly affect predictions. Notable variables such as Fund Number \times GDP and Final Close Size exhibit strong non-linear effects, highlighting the ability of ML models to capture performance drivers often missed by traditional econometric approaches.

6.2 Practical Implications

These findings provide actionable insights for LPs and policymakers. For LPs, the dual modelling framework supports decision-making at multiple stages. Classification models, most notably SVC, can efficiently screen large volumes of funds by identifying likely top-quartile performers, supporting due diligence. Regression models, most notably XGBoost, offer continuous NIRR forecasts, enabling more granular comparisons and better alignment with risk-return objectives. SHAP values enhance interpretability by linking predictions to economically meaningful features, helping justify fund selection decisions. Further, retraining models with updated fund or macro data also supports dynamic benchmarking and early detection of underperformance, enabling more proactive portfolio management.

For policymakers, these findings highlight the value of infrastructure that enables transparent, data-driven private market investments. As regulations evolve to encourage institutional exposure in PE, interpretable ML models can support fiduciary oversight by strengthening justifications for private allocations and enhance risk management. In emerging fund-of-

funds structures, such tools may improve capital deployment efficiency through scalable, objective fund evaluation.

6.3 Limitations and Future Research

This study offers meaningful empirical contributions, however several limitations remain, each pointing to avenues for future research.

First, the dataset is limited to 441 buyout and growth equity funds from North America and Europe, reflecting data sparsity and restricted access to proprietary records. This is significant in ML contexts, where larger, more diverse samples improve model robustness and generalisability (Rajput et al., 2023). Future research could address this by incorporating deal-level data, GP disclosures, or investor reports to cover a broader range of fund types, stages, and geographies.

Second, the analysis relies exclusively on structured variables, omitting unstructured data. While structured data captures key financial and operational metrics, it overlooks softer indicators commonly used in LP due diligence. Future research could apply natural language processing (NLP) techniques to extract predictive signals from fund (Sigrist et al., 2023).

Third, this study adopts a cross-sectional design, modelling fund performance as a function of static predictors observed at fund close. Future research could apply time-series methods to capture fund performance dynamics over time.

Combined, these directions offer opportunities to advance ML-based PE forecasting and support more transparent, evidence-driven allocation in private markets.

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Appendices

Appendix A:

Figure A1: VIF Analysis

Appendix B:

Figure B1: Kernel Density Estimates of NIRR across the data transformations

